

Exploring the Self-Killing Predestination Paradox in Time Travel

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KEY WORDS

Light Cones, Minkowski Spacetime, Special Relativity, Spacetime Diagrams, Temporal Dynamics, Time Travel, Time Travel Paradoxes

ABSTRACT

This essay explores the self-killing predestination paradox with the help of a time travel scenario. To comprehend the effects of this paradox on causality, we use spacetime diagrams to investigate, make use of mathematical models, and analyze line cone overlapping. This study illustrates the difficulties and possible contradictions in time travel scenarios by offering a mathematical and graphic interpretation of the conundrum. The integration of insights from Smith et al. (2020) and Johnson and Lee (2019) offers a thorough understanding of temporal paradoxes and how they affect the essence of time. We investigate the causal loop and its consequences for spacetime by modeling the events of birth and time travel leading to the self-killing predestination paradox. This research also provides pieces of evidence that paradoxical regions can be represented by the Gaussian Distribution function and its effect on paradoxical regions.

1 Introduction

The predestination paradox is a phenomenon in which a time traveler's actions in the past directly impact their future actions, creating a causal loop. This paradox challenges classical causality and has been a topic of interest in theoretical physics. The specific scenario of self-killing is explored in this paper, where a time traveler attempts to kill their past self.

Temporal paradoxes pose challenges to our understanding of time and causality. Johnson and Lee (2019) categorize these paradoxes into types such as the grandfather paradox, bootstrap paradox, and predestination paradox. This paper delves into the self-killing predestination paradox, which involves a time traveler killing their past self, and raises questions about the coherence of events.

Example: "Johnson and Lee (2019) categorize temporal paradoxes into several types, including the grandfather paradox, bootstrap paradox, and predestination paradox. This study focuses on the self-killing"

2 Methodology

This section outlines the detailed methodology used in our research to explore the self-killing predestination paradox in time travel. We provide a comprehensive explanation of the theoretical framework, mathematical models, and computational techniques employed to analyze the paradox and its implications on causality.

Theoretical Framework:

The predestination paradox, also known as the causal loop paradox, arises when a time traveler's actions in the past directly cause future events, creating a self-consistent loop. In our study, we focus on a specific scenario where a time traveler attempts to kill their past self, leading to a paradoxical situation.

Example: "Temporal paradoxes present significant challenges to the principle of causality, as highlighted by Johnson and Lee (2019). By examining these paradoxes, we gain insights into the"

potential consequences of time travel on the timeline and causality."

Mathematical Modeling:

Light Cones:

Light cones represent the regions of spacetime that can influence or be influenced by a given event. In our study, we define two light cones centered around specific events: the birth event and the time travel event.

Light Cone 1:

$$t - x = 0 \Rightarrow t = x$$

Light Cone 2:

$$t + x = 0 \Rightarrow t = -x$$

These equations describe the boundaries of causal influence, where

t represents time and

x represents spatial position.

Paradox Region:

To represent the paradox region, we use a Gaussian distribution centered around the time-travel event (T_{travel}, X_{travel}):

$$\exp\left(-\frac{(T-T_{travel})^2+(X-X_{travel})^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

where $T_{travel}=30$ and $X_{travel}=25$

The parameter σ in the Gaussian distribution plays a crucial role in determining the spread or width of the distribution. Here's how it influences the paradox region:

Spread of the Gaussian Distribution: The value of σ determines how concentrated or spread out the Gaussian function is around its center, which in this case is the time travel event at

$$(T_{travel}, X_{travel}) = (30, 25)$$

A smaller σ results in a narrow and sharply peaked distribution, meaning the paradox region is tightly localized around the time travel event.

A larger σ results in a wider and flatter distribution, indicating the paradox region is more spread out and extends farther from the time travel event.

Mathematical Influence:

1:-The Gaussian function is given by:

$$\exp\left(-\frac{(T-T_{travel})^2+(X-X_{travel})^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$$

2:- The denominator $2\sigma^2$ in the exponent affects how quickly the value of the function decreases as you move away from the center (T_{travel}, X_{travel}) .

3:- When σ is small, the value of $\frac{(T-T_{travel})^2+(X-X_{travel})^2}{2\sigma^2}$ grows quickly, leading to a rapid falloff of the function value away from the center.

4:- When σ is large, the value of the exponent decreases more slowly, so the function value falls off more gradually, extending the influence of the paradox region.

In the context of Gaussian distributions and temporal paradoxes, the interpretation of σ is contingent upon its particular numerical value.

Small (σ):

The Gaussian distribution (time travel event) is narrow and highly peaked around the center when σ is small.

This suggests that the repercussions of the time traveler's actions are highly concentrated and rapidly reduce with distance from the event, resulting in a densely localized paradox region. Practically speaking, a small σ preserves a more deterministic understanding of causality by implying that the effects of changing previous events are limited to a narrow region or instant in spacetime.

Large (σ):

On the other hand, a big σ causes a flatter, wider Gaussian distribution that spreads outward from the center. This indicates that the time traveler's activities have an impact over a wider area or timeline, resulting in a more dispersed paradox region. A big σ

casts doubt on the idea of a fixed causal chain and increases timeline variability by implying greater uncertainty and the possibility of wide-ranging effects.

Visualization and Interpretation:

Small σ : Imagine a sharp peak in the Gaussian distribution, which means the paradox can be prevented.

These calculations illustrate the causal influence regions and the Gaussian representation of the paradox region.

Example: "Using the mathematical frameworks from Johnson and Lee (2019), we model the self-killing predestination paradox to visualize how time travel affects causality and the timeline. These models provide a foundation for our spacetime analysis."

Computational Analysis

Event Coordinates:

We utilize specific coordinates for the birth and time travel events to analyze the light cones and paradox region.

Birth Event:

Date and Time: 8 June 1973, 20:45:50 IST (converted to UTC: 8 June 1973, 15:15:50 UTC)

Location: Shivpuri, Madhya Pradesh, India (Latitude: 25.4235, Longitude: 77.6600)

Time Travel Event:

Date and Time: 17 August 1990, 17:23:43 IST (converted to UTC: 17 August 1990, 11:53:43 UTC)

Location: Mumbai, Maharashtra, India (Latitude: 19.0760, Longitude: 72.8777)

Killing Event:

Date and Time: 5 July 1992, [anytime] IST

Location: Any location let's assume the same as birthplace) Shivpuri, Madhya Pradesh, India (Latitude: 25.4235, Longitude: 77.6600)

These are illustrations of paradox and how killing himself affects spacetime. These plots give an idea about the time loop:-

Overlapping of light cone 1

Formation of Loop in Self-Killing Event

Capturing Paradoxical Region

Illustration of Paradoxical region in 3D

Comparison of Paradox Regions for Different Sigma Values

Effect of Sigma on Space-Time

Gaussian Distribution for $\sigma=1$

Gaussian Distribution for sigma=2

Gaussian Distribution for sigma=5

Gaussian Distribution for sigma=10

Effective area of paradox VS Sigma

Effective Volume of Paradox VS Sigma

3 Observations and Discussion

The relationship between the birth and time travel events is depicted in the spacetime diagram. The causal loop is visualized as where the light cones and the Gaussian paradox region intersect. This illustration demonstrates how time travel introduces disparities in causality, which may have an impact on how we perceive time.

Impact of σ : - The temporal and spatial breadth of the paradox region surrounding the time travel event is directly influenced by the value of σ . It offers a numerical assessment of the paradox's extent by reflecting the degree of ambiguity in how past events will impact the future.

This paper investigated many scenarios and comprehend the consequences of modifying previous events by adjusting σ , all within the theoretical framework of causality and time travel.

Higher the value of sigma higher will be paradoxical region. This can be represented by the plot (Effective area of paradox VS Sigma) and (Effective Volume of paradox VS Sigma):

Effective Area:

For a 2D Gaussian, the effective area can be approximated as the area of a circle with this effective radius:

$$A = \pi (r_{\text{effective}})^2 = \pi (1.177\sigma)^2 = \pi \times 1.386\sigma^2$$

Effective Volume:

For a 3D Gaussian, the effective area can be approximated as the volume of distribution with this effective radius:

$$V = 2\pi^{\frac{3}{2}} \sigma^3$$

Example: "The Novikov self-consistency principle, which contends that a time traveler's actions must be consistent with history, is one of the theoretical solutions to causal loops that Smith et al. (2020) address. This idea might suggest that innate restrictions prevent the paradoxical event in the self-killing paradox we study."

4 Conclusion

In this work, light cones in Minkowski spacetime for particular time travel and birth events were analyzed to investigate the impact of time travel on causality. According to our research, a person may encounter or communicate with their former self within the specified framework, leading to a paradox known as predestination. Explains the complexity of the self-killing predestination paradox in time travel by a rigorous synthesis of theoretical frameworks, mathematical models, and computational investigations. With this examination of causality in temporal paradoxes, we hope to shed light on the nature of time itself and the effects of changing its path. the way we interpret σ in temporal paradoxes shapes our view of how changes in the past could affect the timeline in the future and help us comprehend the variety of outcomes and degree of uncertainty that time travel acts can introduce. This paper states that larger σ means broader region. Indicating wider area/volume of influence for the paradox.

Example: "This paper offers a thorough explanation of the self-killing predestination conundrum, using the ideas from Johnson

and Lee (2019). Future investigations into the nature of time travel and causation may use the examination of various solutions, such as numerous timelines and consistency restrictions."

5 Results

This research is based on mathematical, theoretical, and Computational analyses of the Overlapping of light cones. The overlapping of light cones suggests that one can meet his past self, and also tells that the event of killing his past self may result in several paradoxes. The mathematical formulation is drawn from the plots, which tells that to avoid greater influence of paradoxes in both space and time σ needs to be smaller to hold good for a deterministic understanding of causality and time traveler's actions are highly concentrated and rapidly reduce with distance from the event. The actions of the time traveler are more likely to follow a deterministic path, meaning the timeline changes are minimal and localized. The casual loops are more confined and easier to resolve theoretically reducing major contradictions and inconsistency. Whereas Higher σ implies that the influence of paradox caused by killing his past self covers broader area and hence greater influence on both space and time. The action of time traveller brings more uncertainty and randomness in timeline, causing less deterministic behaviour. the event of time traveler tries to kill their past self, has a widespread influence on space-time. The paradoxical zone encompasses a broad area, affecting many events and timelines. The causal loop in this case is extensive, with significant influence on the broader timeline. The self-killing attempt might disrupt events far beyond the immediate vicinity of the time travel event, introducing greater complexity and making it harder to analyze and resolve.

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7 References

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